

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Project READ (Reading Enhancement for Academic Development): A Reading Program for Pupils of Kalliat Integrated School

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the reading performance of Grade VI pupils at Kalliat Integrated School, focusing on their comprehension skills after participating in Project READ (Reading Enhancement for Academic Development). Using the Apayao Literacy Engagement Advancement Program (LEAP) reading rubrics, the research assessed pupils' reading levels before and after the intervention through a pre-test–posttest one-shot design. Fourteen pupils were identified as beneficiaries, all of whom initially struggled with text comprehension. Pretest results revealed that their reading levels dropped to the Sentence level, highlighting the urgent need for intervention. The program was implemented over 16 weeks and consisted of one-on-one guided reading sessions and comprehension exercises. Posttest findings showed marked improvement in pupils' reading performance. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences when grouped by sex, ethnicity, or parents' educational attainment, though age was found to have a significant effect. Importantly, there was a significant difference in reading levels before and after the intervention, confirming the effectiveness of Project READ. The study concludes that Project READ successfully enhanced pupils' reading comprehension and overall performance. It recommends sustaining the program and exploring additional reading initiatives to further support literacy development in the primary grades.

Keywords: Project READ; Literacy; Assessment; Descriptive

1. Introduction

Reading is crucial at all educational levels because it improves academic achievement and is required for all course material. Reading performances and severe reading failures motivates researchers to look for innovative reading approaches through reading programs nationally (Kletzien, 1996). The Chinese government has been pushing reading instruction because they believe that it increases children' academic achievement (Chan and Chiu, 2024).

The Philippines is firm in its campaign that every Filipino learner is a reader. Reading innovations through reading programs in every school are highly promoted to eradicate the low academic performances of every struggling learner. However, the Philippines' dismal reading performance, which caused the nation to receive the lowest overall rating in the world, only serves to highlight how little progress is being made by schools in producing educated citizens of high caliber (Librea et. al, 2023). Additionally, educators and legislators have found it difficult to address the reading proficiency of Filipino pupils. Therefore, a strategic intervention reading program has been developed. The Philippines' government has been working to raise the country's literacy rates, but new research indicates that many children still require assistance with vocabulary growth, reading comprehension, and critical thinking. Areas for improvement as well as the current reading proficiency of Filipino kids. A lack of resources and socioeconomic conditions are two of the reasons for the low reading abilities. However, some possible areas for development have been highlighted, including funding teacher training, encouraging early literacy initiatives, and creating interesting and culturally appropriate reading materials for Filipino pupils (Romey and Zabala Jr. 2023).

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Moreover, the relationship between reading level and reading strategies affects reading proficiency level. Thus, there should be innovations to improve their comprehension of reading texts and their mastery of reading strategies (Austria and Ramos, 2024). Effective teaching methods also included exposing non-readers to letter sounds, brief stories, and follow-up while using teachers' modifications, tactics, and scaffolds to create reading competence. The effectiveness of students' reading is significantly influenced by reading teachers' natures as enablers, facilitators, humanists, behaviorists, and experts about their teaching approaches (Duque and Fortes, 2023). Phonemic awareness is also a vital skill that must be taught before the other components to be a good reader, must be taught first in the acquisition process of the components of learning to read, namely: phonics; vocabulary; fluency; and comprehension (Alvarez et. al, 2023).

With the DepEd goal that every learner, a reader, varied teaching methods and reading programs were conducted in the country. Reading programs with the use of board games, flash card-based lessons, and reading tutorial films (Ibo and Mandarin, 2023), Project Tati Tore (Take Time to Read) carried out using watching movies, forced reading, and free reading wherein 16 students improved their reading proficiency following the three-week program (Viray, 2023); Multimodal Reading Instruction (MRI) for reading fluency using linguistic, visual, and auditory modalities to experience, comprehend, analyze, and create multimodal writings (Rugunda and Patiño, 2025).; Balsa Para sa Pagbasa involving 30-minute Purok-based reading remedial program improved the level of reading performance of students in Grade 5 of Maazim Central Elementary School, showed that the program was an advantageous experience (Manegdeg and Paglinawan, 2025).; and Oplan to hang with 30-minute classroom-based tutorial program of Maasim Central Elementary School (Aguirre et. Al, 2024) and Project ELL program of San Roque Elementary School improved learners' literacy skills through audio-visual (Tribujeña et. al, 2025). The Alpbasa game-based reading program of St. Paul University Philippines carried out 18 days of teaching reading in kindergarten and elementary as it incorporates music, movements, costumes theatrical presentations and supplemental activities in learning revealed that the exposure of non-readers to it resulted in better performance of the students in reading. Through action songs and movement-based activities, pupils are geared to play with language as learning situations are made concrete and realistic; thus, making reading more effective, interesting, and engaging (Masigan, (2020).

Moreover, the use of PBL and DRTA increases the critical thinking and reading comprehension skills of Grade 2 elementary pupils (Utomo and Syamsi, 2019), pupils who received the PBL approach achieve higher performance in reading (Sidik and Masek, 2021), and the use of DRTA shows that there is a significant difference using guided reading procedure (Yeny and Nadjmuddin, 2020).

Therefore, in support of the Brigada Pagbasa Program of DepEd., the Schools Division of Apayao, massively promotes the campaign on reading programs as it intensifies the advocacy for reading under the Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiatives) issued under Memorandum No.173 s, 2019, and DepEd Memorandum No.44 s. 2021. This Brigada Pagbasa dubbed as Project PAGBATAYAM in Apayao aims to promote massive awareness of the impact of reading skills on the performances of the learners in the school community (Pocan et. al, 2022).

In response to the call, Kalliat Integrated School of Kabugao District 2 adopted a Brigada Pagbasa program named Project READ (Reading Enhancement for Academic Development) aims to cater the struggling readers, especially in their reading performances towards their reading progress. Reading methods and strategies used in the programs meant to aid every struggling learner are implemented through one-on-one guided reading and collaboration in a 40-minute reading session. This reading remediation program aimed to improve every learner especially to their reading comprehension skills.

As an implementer of Project READ, the researcher was motivated to assess the implementation among the learners of Kalliat Integrated School of Kabugao District 2 to ascertain its effect in improving the reading performance of struggling readers.

2. Research Question

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Project READ (Reading Enhancement for Academic Development) as a reading program for struggling readers of Kalliat Integrated School, EKB, Lenneng, Kabugao, Apayao.

Specifically, it was guided by the following questions

- What is the profile of the Grade VI pupils according to age, sex, ethnicity, and educational attainment of parents?
- What is the reading comprehension level of the participants before the implementation of Project READ?
- What is the reading comprehension level of the participants after the implementation of Project READ?

- What is the reading comprehension level of the participants when grouped according to profile?

Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the participants when grouped according to profile?

Is there is a significant difference in the reading comprehension level of the participants before and after the implementation of Project READ.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The study made used of a pretest, posttest, and one group research design. It determined the effect of Project READ as a reading remediation program towards improved reading performance of pupils of Kalliat Integrated School, S.Y. 2023-2024.

3.2. Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Kalliat Integrated School (KIS) during the third and fourth quarter of the S.Y. 2023-2024.

3.3. Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were the Grade VI class of the school. A total of 14 pupils enrolled in Kalliat Integrated School for the SY 2023-2024. Total enumeration was applied.

3.4. Research Instrument

The researcher employed a 40-item standardized pretest and posttest in reading lifted from Apayao Literacy Engagement and Advancement Program (LEAP). A pretest and posttest used the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT) and Apayao Literacy Engagement and Advancement Program (LEAP) reading materials. The test measured the level of reading of pupils as to Sentence level, paragraph level, short stories with less than 150 words level and short stories with more than 150 words level. The rubrics used was taken from the Literacy Engagement and Advancement Program (LEAP) presented as follows:

3.5. Data Gathering Procedure

Table 1 Rubrics for scoring the reading levels of the pupils

Reading Levels	Interpretation
Sentence Level	If the pupil can read 58 words and above with ease and fluency and was able to answer 9 to 10 questions correctly. Proceed to the next level. If the pupil can only read below 57 words and be able to answer 6 to 8 questions correctly, stop here, no need to proceed to the next level.
Short Paragraph level	If the pupil can read 78 words and above with ease and fluency and was able to answer 9 to 10 questions correctly. Proceed to the next level. If the pupil can only read 77 words and below and be able to answer 6 to 8 questions correctly, stop here. No need to proceed to the next level.
Short stories with less than 150 words	If the pupil can read 103 words and above and can be able to answer 9 to 10 questions correctly. Proceed to the next level. If the pupil can read 102 words and below and can be able to answer 6 to 8 questions, stop here. No need to proceed to the next level.
Short stories with more than 150 words	If the pupil can read 256 words and below and can answer 6 to 8 questions correctly, mark the pupil at "Short Stories with less than 150 words". If the pupil can read 257 words and above and can answer 9 to 10 questions correctly then the pupil is declared an INDEPENDENT READER.

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Apayao, the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of Kabugao District 2 and the School Head of Kalliat Integrated School. After which, a pretest was administered by the researcher. The participants were engaged in a 40-minute reading session after class within 16

weeks for the implementation of Project READ. After it, A post-test was administered to the Grade VI pupils. The results were tabulated, consolidated, and analyzed by the researcher with the assistance of the statistician.

3.6. Statistical Analysis

Frequency and Percentage was computed for the profile of Grade VI pupils. Meanwhile, mean, and standard deviation were computed on the performance of the pupils in the pre-test and post-test. T-tests was employed to determine the significant difference in the performance in reading before and after the reading remediation and when grouped according to profile.

4. Results And Discussion

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of participants according to age, Sex, Ethnicity, educational attainment of parents

Profile	Frequency	%
1. Age		
11 years old	3	21.43
12 years old	7	50.00
13 years old	2	14.29
14 years old	1	7.14
15 years old	1	7.14
Total	14	100.00
Mean Age= 12.29 years old		
2. Sex		
Male	10	71.43
Female	4	28.57
Total	14	100.00
3. Ethnicity		
Isang	4	28.57
Kanaani	10	71.43
Total	14	100.00
4. Father's Educational Attainment		
Elem Level	11	78.57
Elem Grad	1	7.14
HS Level	1	7.14
College Level	1	7.14
Total	14	100.00
5. Mother's Educational Attainment		
Elem Level	12	85.71
Elem Grad	2	14.29
Total	14	100.00

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the 14 Grade VI participants according to age, sex, ethnicity, and parents' educational attainment. The majority of pupils, 7 or 50%, are 12 years old, with a mean age of 12.29, indicating that most are at the appropriate age for their grade level, although two are overage. In terms of sex, 10 or 71.43% are male while only 4 or 28.57% are female, showing a predominance of male pupils. Ethnicity-wise, 10 or 71.43% belong to the Kankana-ey group compared to 4 or 28.57% from the Isnag group, reflecting the larger presence of Kankana-ey settlers in the community. Regarding fathers' educational attainment, the majority, 11 or 78.57%,

reached only the elementary level, with very few attaining higher education. Similarly, mothers' educational attainment is concentrated at the elementary level, with 12 or 85.71% not progressing beyond it. Overall, the table highlights that most respondents are of the right age for Grade VI, predominantly male, largely Kankana-ey, and come from families where parents' education is limited to the elementary level.

Table 3 Reading comprehension level of the participants before the implementation of Project READ

Reading Comprehension Level	Freq	Percentage
Sentence Level	14	100.00
Short Paragraph Level	0	0.00
Short Stories with less than 150 words	0	0.00
Short Stories with more than 150 words	0	0.00
Total	14	100.00

Table 3 shows the pre-test results using the Apayao Literacy and Advancement Program (LEAP), guided by Division Memorandum No. 476 s. 2023, revealed that all 14 participants demonstrated reading comprehension only at the Sentence Level, with none able to progress to short paragraphs or stories. This indicates that pupils could read fewer than 57 words and answer only 6–8 questions correctly, reflecting poor comprehension skills prior to the implementation of Project READ.

Such findings align with Estremera and Estremera, (2018), who reported similar challenges among Grade VI pupils in Sorsogon, Philippines, where low comprehension levels prompted the adoption of targeted reading intervention strategies. These parallel underscores the urgent need for systematic programs like Project READ to strengthen learners' reading proficiency and comprehension.

Table 4 Reading comprehension level of the participants after the implementation of Project READ

Reading Comprehension Level	Freq	Percentage
Sentence Level	0	0.00
Short Paragraph Level	0	0.00
Short Stories with less than 150 words	5	35.70
Short Stories with more than 150 words	9	64.30
Total	14	100.00

In table 4, after the implementation of Project READ, significant improvement in pupils' reading comprehension was observed, as none remained at the sentence or paragraph level; instead, 35.70% progressed to reading short stories with fewer than 150 words, while 64.30% advanced to reading longer stories exceeding 150 words. This outcome demonstrates that most learners can now read 257 words or more and correctly answer 9 to 10 comprehension questions, qualifying them as independent readers. The success of Project READ, aligned with the Brigada Pagbasa Program and the 3Bs Initiatives of DepEd, highlights the effectiveness of one-on-one guided reading interventions in enhancing comprehension skills.

Consistent with Falth, (2013), these results affirm that targeted interventions can foster positive progress in pupils' reading abilities, thereby addressing the challenges of struggling readers and promoting academic development.

Table 5 Reading comprehension level of the pupils before and after Project READ when grouped according to age

Profile (age)	Before Project READ		After Project READ			
	Reading Comprehension Level		Reading Comprehension Level			
	Sentence Level		Short Stories with less than 150 words		Short Stories with less than 150 words	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
11 years old	3	21.43	1	7.14	2	14.29
12 years old	7	50.00	1	7.14	6	42.86
13 years old	2	14.29	2	14.29	0	0.00
14 years old	1	7.14	0	0.00	1	7.14
15 years old	1	7.14	1	7.14	0	0.00
Total	14	100.00	5	35.71	9	64.29

In table 5, before the implementation of Project READ, all pupils across age groups demonstrated only a Sentence Level of reading comprehension, indicating limited ability to process texts. However, after the program, notable improvements were observed, with pupils progressing to higher levels of comprehension. Specifically, six 12-year-old pupils advanced to reading short stories with more than 150 words, showing the greatest improvement among the age groups. Meanwhile, 11-year-olds and 14-year-olds also showed progress, with some reaching the level of short stories, while 13- and 15-year-olds displayed mixed results, with a few remaining at lower levels. Overall, the data highlights that Project READ effectively enhanced reading comprehension, particularly among 12-year-old learners, demonstrating the program's impact in fostering independent reading skills across varying ages.

Table 6 Reading comprehension level of the participants before and after Project READ when grouped according to Sex

Profile (Sex)	Before Project READ		After Project READ			
	Reading Comprehension Level		Reading Comprehension Level			
	Sentence Level		Short Stories with less than 150 words		Short Stories with more than 150 words	
	F	%	F	%	f	%
Male	10	71.43	5	35.71	5	35.71
Female	4	28.57	0	0.00	4	28.57
Total	14	100.00	5	35.71	9	64.29

In table 6, before the implementation of Project READ, both male and female pupils were limited to the Sentence Level of reading comprehension. After the program, however, notable progress was achieved: 35.71% of male pupils advanced to reading short stories with fewer than 150 words, while 28.57% of female pupils reached the higher level of reading short stories with more than 150 words. This indicates that although more males showed improvement at

the lower short story level, female pupils demonstrated stronger advancement by attaining the highest reading comprehension level. Overall, the results highlight that Project READ effectively enhanced reading skills across sexes, with female pupils emerging as the group with the highest reading proficiency.

Table 7 Reading comprehension level of the participants before and after Project READ when grouped according to Ethnicity

Profile (Ethnicity)	Before Project READ		After Project READ			
	Reading Comprehension Level		Reading Comprehension Level			
	SL		SS LESS		SSMORE	
	F	%	f	%	F	%
Isang	4	28.57	2	14.29	2	14.29
Kanaani	10	71.43	2	14.29	8	57.14
Total	14	100.00	4	28.58	10	71.43

In table 7, before the implementation of Project READ, pupils from both the Isang and Kanaani ethnic groups were limited to the Sentence Level of reading comprehension. After the program, however, their performance improved, with 14.29% from each group progressing to short stories with fewer than 150 words. More notably, 57.14% of Kankana-ey pupils advanced to reading short stories with more than 150 words, compared to 14.29% of Isang pupils at the same level. This indicates that while both groups benefited from the intervention, the Kankana-ey pupils achieved the highest reading comprehension level, highlighting the effectiveness of Project READ in fostering independent reading skills across ethnic groups, with particularly strong gains among Kankana-ey learners.

Table 8 Reading comprehension level of the participants before and after Project READ when grouped according to educational attainment

Profile (Educational attainment)	Before Project READ		After Project READ			
	Reading Comprehension Level		Reading Comprehension Level			
	Sentence Level		Short Stories with less than 150 words		Short Stories with less than 150 words	
	F	%	f	%	F	%
Father's Educational Attainment						
Elem Level	11	78.57	4	28.57	7	50.00
Elem Grad	1	7.14	0	0.00	1	7.14
HS Level	1	7.14	0	0.00	1	7.14
College Level	1	7.14	1	7.14	0	0.00
Total	14	100.00	5	35.71	9	64.29

Mother's Educational Attainment						
Elem Level	12	85.71	4	28.57	8	57.14
Elem Grad	2	14.29	1	7.14	1	7.14
Total	14	100.00	5	35.71	9	64.29

In table 8, before the implementation of Project READ, all pupils regardless of their parents' educational attainment were limited to the Sentence Level of reading comprehension, with the majority coming from families where both father (78.57%) and mother (85.71%) had only reached the elementary level. After the program, however, substantial progress was observed: 50% of pupils whose fathers had elementary-level education advanced to reading short stories with more than 150 words, while 57.14% of pupils whose mothers had the same educational background achieved the same level, making them independent readers. Additionally, pupils whose fathers were elementary graduates and high school level, as well as those whose mothers were elementary graduates, also showed improvement by reaching higher comprehension levels. These results imply that Project READ effectively enhanced reading skills across pupils regardless of parental educational attainment, with the highest gains seen among those whose parents had elementary-level education.

Table 9 Test of Significant difference in the reading comprehension of the participants when grouped according to profile

Profile Variables	t-value	DF	p-value	Decision at $\alpha= 0.05$
Sex	-1.343	12	0.204	Accept Ho
Ethnicity	.279	12	0.785	Accept Ho
Profile Variables	F-value	DF	p-value	Decision at $\alpha= 0.05$
Age	5.092	4,9	0.020	Reject Ho
Father's Educational attainment	0.159	3,10	0.922	Accept Ho
Mother's Educational attainment	0.205		0.659	Accept Ho

Table 9 shows that there is a significant difference in the reading comprehension of pupils when grouped according to age, while no significant differences were found when grouped according to sex, ethnicity, or parents' educational attainment. This finding aligns with studies such as those of Almondsbury and Corlet, (2023), which reported that sex does not play a necessary role in reading performance, though contrasting evidence from Fauzan, (2016) suggested girls often outperform boys in comprehension ability. Similarly, Koskei et. al, (2016), found parental educational attainment did not significantly influence reading performance, though Milanese and Pascual, (2023) argued that higher parental education could lead to better comprehension, with Roque et al. (2023), noting some implications of parental attainment on children's reading abilities. Ethnicity also showed no significant relationship with comprehension levels. In contrast, age was found to be a key factor, as younger pupils tended to achieve higher comprehension scores than older or over-aged learners, consistent with Libao and Montejo, (2024), though contradicted by Vlachos, and Papadimitriou, (2015), who found older children performed better. These results suggest that while sex, ethnicity, and parental education may not strongly affect reading comprehension, age plays a critical role, highlighting the need for teachers to provide additional support to older pupils who may struggle compared to their younger peers.

Table 10 Test significant difference in the reading comprehension level of the participants before and after the implementation of Project READ

Reading Comprehension	T	DF	P	Decision at $\alpha= 0.05$
Before the implementation of Project READ	-19.887	13	.000000000001	Reject Ho
After the implementation of Project READ				

The results in Table 10 reveal a highly significant difference in the reading comprehension levels of pupils before and after the implementation of Project READ, as indicated by the very low p-value which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Pupils' reading levels improved from the Sentence Level during the pre-test to Short Stories with less than 150 words and Short Stories with more than 150 words in the post-test, proving the effectiveness of Project READ as a reading intervention. The program's one-on-one guided reading and comprehension exercises provided genuine engagement and sufficient time for each pupil, enabling them to become independent readers. This outcome parallels the findings of Alvarez et. al, 2023, who emphasized the importance of pedagogical practices in developing reading skills, and aligns with Higuera and Cacho, 2022, who warned that neglecting comprehension can weaken literacy foundations. Similarly, it supports the study of Ibo and Mandarin, 2023, on the Tati Tore (Take Time to Read) Program, which highlighted the necessity of designing school-based interventions that cater to varying reading levels. Overall, Project READ successfully enhanced pupils' comprehension abilities, underscoring the value of structured and individualized reading programs in fostering literacy development.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the implementation of Project READ (Reading Enhancement for Academic Development) proved to be a highly effective intervention in improving the reading comprehension skills of struggling pupils. From initially performing only at the Sentence Level, learners advanced to reading short stories of varying lengths, with many achieving independent reader status. The program's structured one-on-one guided reading sessions and comprehension exercises provided meaningful engagement, strengthened literacy foundations, and fostered confidence in reading. Overall, Project READ demonstrated that targeted, school-based interventions can significantly enhance pupils' reading performance, thereby supporting their academic growth and aligning with broader educational initiatives to ensure that every child becomes a successful reader.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

I acknowledge that I have not used ChatGPT or Copilot for refining some of the sections in the document.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Consent (wherever applicable)

I affirm that the respondents voluntarily agreed to participate after being fully informed about the purpose, nature, and potential implications of the study. Their responses have been collected with utmost respect for their privacy and confidentiality, in accordance with ethical research guidelines.

Statement of ethical approval

The study was conducted with approval and in accordance with the standards of the college. No ethical approval was required, as the research followed all applicable ethical guidelines, ensuring respect for the respondents' privacy and confidentiality

Statement of informed consent

Author have declared that they have no known competing financial interests OR non-financial interests OR personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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